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Influence of Occupational and Personal Factors on Temporomandibular Joint Disorders in the North Gujarat Population - A Cross Sectional Study

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Abstract

Background: Temporomandibular disorders (TMDs) are among the most prevalent and painful musculoskeletal conditions involving symptoms like jaw pain, limited mouth opening, joint noises, and mandibular deviation. TMD prevalence varies across populations. Psychological distress, including anxiety, depression, occupational hazards, sleep disturbances and pain has been consistently associated with TMD. Emerging evidence from prospective research suggests that psychological distress may not only accompany but also precede the development of TMD, indicating its potential role as a key risk factor. This study aims to assess the influence of occupational and personal factors in TMD development and persistence in different age groups. Total 200 patients were assessed using a preformed questionnaire through Google Form consisting of 22 questions regarding their demographic information and related to their work and stress. All the participants were selected according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The results showed a strong association ($p < 0.05$) between occupation, working hours, and sleeping hours in different age groups, with the 21-30 yrs age group being the most affected group associated with TMD symptoms.

Keywords: Occupational stress, Personal stress, Psychological stress, Temporomandibular Joint disorders

INTRODUCTION

Temporomandibular disorders (TMDs) are common and often distressing conditions that affect the temporomandibular joint (TMJ) and the surrounding masticatory muscles. Ranking just behind back pain as the most prevalent musculoskeletal issue, TMDs typically manifest as jaw discomfort, difficulty opening the mouth, joint sounds near the ears, and deviation during jaw movements.¹ These disorders are generally divided into two main categories, i.e. pain-related conditions, such as muscle disorders and inflammation of the TMJ capsule, and intra-articular conditions such as disc displacement and TMJ osteoarthritis. The occurrence of TMD symptoms varies widely across populations, with estimates ranging from 1.8% to over 30%. The global economic impact is considerable, with costs surpassing \$100 billion annually in the United States alone. Asian countries like South Korea have also reported a significant rise in both diagnosis rates and healthcare spending related to TMD.²

TMDs are known to arise from a combination of biological and psychosocial factors. Physically, causes may include jaw trauma, teeth grinding, bite misalignment, and excessive stress on the TMJ. In addition, environmental and lifestyle factors such as job-related stress, financial strain, and overall

mental well-being are increasingly recognized as important contributors. Although multiple risk factors have been identified, their individual and combined roles in TMD development remain unclear and warrant further investigation.³

A growing body of research supports the influence of psychological factors on TMD. Individuals suffering from chronic TMD pain often report greater emotional distress, poor sleep, somatic symptoms, and a tendency to catastrophize. Furthermore, those with pre-existing emotional disturbances such as anxiety or depression appear more likely to develop TMD over time. While much of the current evidence focuses on those already diagnosed, emerging longitudinal studies suggest that mental health issues may not only exacerbate symptoms but could also contribute to the onset of TMD in at-risk individuals.⁴

Although there has been limited studies determining the association of occupational and personal risk factors that are counted to be hazardous in developing TMD related symptoms particularly pain; this questionnaire based study was an approach to collect the associative occupational and personal risk factors involved in TMD related symptoms in different age groups.

METHODOLOGY

The questionnaire-based study was conducted on 200 patients diagnosed with Temporomandibular Joint Disorder (TMD) reported to the department of Oral Medicine & Radiology, Narsinhbhai Patel Dental College and Hospital, Visnagar. The questionnaire was prepared in google form which contained 22 questions related to patients personal information, and related to occupation, working hours, sleeping hours, stress related to family, studies or financial status.

Questionnaire

1. Name of patient
2. Age / Gender (___yrs, M /F)
3. Education Level (10th pass, 12th pass, Graduate, Post graduate, Ph.D, post. Doctorate)
4. Occupation (Agriculture, Health worker etc.)
5. Designation (Admin level job, Student etc.)
6. Working Hours (>9 hours, <9hours, 9hours)
7. Sleep Hours (>6 hours, <6hours, 6 hours)
8. Whether the patient is feeling stressful about their life? (Yes / No)
9. Stress related to (Financial / Family /Exam / Health / Other)
10. Head Type (Brachycephalic / Dolicocephalic / Mesocephalic)
11. Occlusion type (Angle's Class-1 / Class-2 / Class-3)
12. Dentition (Dentulous / Partially Edentulous / Completely Edentulous)
13. Previous Dental Visits (if any)
14. Diet (Vegetarian / Eggitarian / Non-vegetarian)
15. Oral destructive habit (Lip biting / Cheek biting / Clenching / Bruxism)
16. Pain VAScore (ranging between 1-10)
17. TM Joint sound (Audible / Not Audible)
18. TM Joint Sound (Unilateral / Bilateral)
19. TM Joint Sound occurs during (Opening / Closing)
20. Tenderness, if present (Yes / No)
21. Restricted MO if present (Yes / No)
22. Jaw deviation if present (Yes / No)

In a few questions patients were allowed to choose multiple options.

The study was conducted after receiving informed consent from all the willing participants/patients.

The responses obtained were grouped according to gender (male & female) and age group of patients (10 to 20, 21 to 30, 31 to 40, 41 to 50, 51 to 60, and 61 to 70 years) for analysis.

RESULT

Among 200 participants, the gender distribution was slightly female predominant than male population with 104 (51.7%) females and 96 (48.3%) males. The distribution of patients according to their sleeping hours showed 22 (11%) patients with <6 hours of sleep, 62 (31%) patients with exactly 6 hours of sleep and 116 (58%) patients with >6 hours of sleep. According to the daily working hours the data showed that 105 (52.2%) patients worked more than 9 hours, 42 (20.9%) patients worked for less than 9 hours and 53 (26.9%) patients worked exactly for 9 hours. Stress perception varied significantly by gender, with 56 (53.33%) males more likely to report feeling stressed, while 73 (70.19%) females responded "No" to the question. The data of type of head among both the genders showed that mesocephalic was the most common head type in both genders with 50 (25%) males and 56 (28%) females having total 106 (53%) patients with a significant gender head type association. The data of previous dental visits in both the genders showed that 79 (39.5%) patients with 45 (22.5%) male and 34 (17%) female whom have never visited a dentist followed by 73 (36.5%) patients with single dental visit, 25 (12.5%) patients with occasional dental visits and 23 (11.5%) patients with frequent dental visits. Patient distribution according to diet type showed 151(75.5%) vegetarian patients, 33(16.5%) eggitarian patients and 16(8%) non - vegetarian patients. The distribution of patients according to oral destructive habits; 129 (64.5%) patients showed no oral destructive habits followed by 24 (12%) patients with lip biting, 21(11%) with bruxism, 14 (7%) with cheek biting and 12 (6%) with clenching. Out of 200 patients, highest number of patients; 94

(47%) patients showed pain VAScore ranging from 6-8 and highest pain VASscore ranging from 9-10 was shown by 62 (31%) patients predominantly in male. Joint sounds were present in 51 (25.5%) participants, with a nearly equal gender distribution. Deviation of jaw was found in 84 (42%) participants, slightly more common in females (23%). The comparison of stress related to different occupations showed that the highest number of patients with private jobs (64.5%) responded "Yes". Across all the occupations, Mesocephalic head type was predominantly found in participants with private jobs (53%). Comparison of oral destructive habits with types of occupation showed no significant relation, though lip biting was frequent among the unemployed (6%) and private workers (3.5%). Financial (28%) and family-related stress (27%) were the most cited causes among 233 responses; work-related stress(0.4%) was rarely reported. Angle's Class I occlusion was predominant (77.1%), with fewer cases of Class II (16.4%) and III malocclusion (3.5%). Among all 200 participants, 166 participants (83.1%) were dentulous, with 25 (12.5%) partially edentulous and 9 (4.5%) completely edentulous. 53 (26.4%) patients reported with restricted mouth opening. The age distribution of patients associated with TMDs showed the highest number of participants (53.5%) belonging to 21–30 years of age group; dominantly seen in females. This age group showed stress related to personal factors rather than occupational factors.

DISCUSSION

Among the study participants, a slight female predilection was observed, reflecting a near-equal gender distribution. A higher prevalence of TMD among working females echoes the observations reported by Nishiyama et al., who found women in high-stress jobs particularly vulnerable.⁵ The majority of individuals reported having more than six hours of sleep per night, with fewer participants getting exactly six or less than six hours. Most of the population worked for more than nine hours a day, followed by those who worked exactly nine or fewer

than nine hours. Similarly, our study's indication that >9 working hours correlates with greater TMD symptoms supports the conclusions by Moustafa et al., both of whom emphasized occupational strain as a significant risk factor.⁶ A significant difference in stress perception was observed between genders, with males more likely to report feeling stressed, while most females denied experiencing stress. Most notably, the observation that males reported more stress conflicts with broader research suggesting that women typically report higher levels of perceived stress.

Mesocephalic head type emerged as the most common cranial form among both genders, showing a significant association with sex. The dominance of mesocephalic head types among participants is in agreement with Sharma Vandana et al., while gender-specific craniofacial differences also show consistency.⁷ A notable proportion of participants had never visited a dentist, while others reported single, occasional, or frequent visits, with females generally demonstrating more proactive dental care behavior these patterns of limited dental visits among males were reported in K. Fukai et al.'s study.⁸ Vegetarianism was the dominant dietary habit, followed by eggitarian and non-vegetarian preferences, though no strong gender link was evident, the higher frequency of vegetarianism among females corroborates the findings of Lombardo and Feraco.^{9,10} Most participants did not exhibit destructive oral habits, but among those who did, lip biting and bruxism were the most frequently observed. These patterns are reflected in published studies: Brazilian school children showed that boys were significantly more likely to exhibit lip-biting and bruxism compared to girls.¹¹ Broader literature indicates that lip/cheek biting and other body-focused repetitive behaviors, including bruxism, are common, with women often exhibiting higher rates of cheek/lip biting overall, but men showing higher lifetime prevalence of some destructive oral habits.¹² Pain intensity varied, with the majority reporting moderate to high levels on the visual analogue scale, and males tending to report

higher scores.¹³ Joint sounds were present in a minority of individuals and distributed almost equally across genders. A systematic review and meta-analysis found that women have approximately twice the odds of experiencing TMD symptoms including joint noises compared to men.¹⁴ Jaw deviation was observed in a significant portion of the population, being slightly more common in females. This aligns with a contemporary clinical profile study by Qin H et al., who found that females were significantly more likely than males to exhibit limitations in jaw movement.¹⁵ Although destructive oral habits did not show a strong occupational pattern, lip biting was more frequently seen among unemployed individuals and private workers. Stress was most commonly reported by individuals working in the private sector, the concentration of TMD in individuals aged 21–30 reflects the trends highlighted by Osiewicz et al.¹⁶ where the mesocephalic head type was also most prevalent.

Personal factors related to financial and family factors was the most commonly reported cause of stress, whereas professional factors were the second most common.

CONCLUSION

The present study concludes that temporomandibular joint disorders are significantly associated with both occupational and personal factors, with young adults particularly females aged 21–30 showing the highest prevalence. Key contributors include long working hours, perceived stress (especially financial and familial), and destructive oral habits, with notable gender differences in stress perception and pain reporting. While mesocephalic head type and vegetarian diets were common, their associations with TMD were not significant. The findings underscore the multifactorial etiology of TMDs and highlight the need for age- and gender-specific preventive and therapeutic approaches.

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TABLES

Table 1: Distribution of patients according to cause of stress and age groups

Cause of Stress	10–20	21–30	31–40	41–50	51–60	61–70	Total
No Cause	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
No Response	0	10	2	1	0	0	13
Other	1	11	7	5	4	1	29
Personal	3	58	28	19	11	4	123
Personal & Professional	0	6	0	0	1	0	7
Professional	2	21	3	1	0	0	27
Total	6	107	40	26	16	5	200

Table 2: Distribution of patients according to gender and cause of stress

Cause of Stress	Female	Male	Total
No Cause	1	0	1
No Response	9	4	13
Other	14	15	29

Table 3: Distribution of patients according to oral destructive habit and occupation type

Oral destructive habit	Occupation					Total	Pearson's Chi Square test
	Health workers	Government jobs	Private job/business	Unemployed /Housewife	Student		
Bruxism	7	2	11	1	0		$\chi^2=359,df=310, p=0.27$
Cheek biting	2	0	10	2	0		
Lip biting	2	0	12	7	2		
Clenching	2	0	9	1	0		
None	17	7	69	32	5		
Total	30	9	111	43	7		

Table 4: Distribution of patients according to occupation type and responses to stress

Responses	Occupation					Total	Pearson's Chi Square test
	Health workers	Government jobs	Private job/business	Unemployed /Housewife	Student		
Yes	16	3	78	27	5	129	$\chi^2=303.23,df=124, p=0.00$
No	14	2	7	3	1	27	
Sometimes	0	4	26	13	1	44	
Total	30	9	111	43	7	200 (100%)	

Table 5: Distribution of patients according to working hours in total number of patients

Work Hr	n	%
< 9 hours	42	20.9%
> 9 hours	105	52.2%
9 hours	53	26.9%
Total	200	100.0%